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Mergers and acquisitions and employees' level of anxiety - the role of HRM practices

Abstract

Anxiety due to organizational change is an important issue in occupational health. The paper presents findings of a study that investigated the level of anxiety experienced by employees due to an acquisition and the effect of human resource management practices in easing anxiety. The sample consisted of employees from both acquiring and target entities, who had experience spanning three phases of merger and acquisition, i.e., pre-, during, and post. The findings showed significant differences in the level of anxiety between the two entities as well as across the three phases. The results showed that human resource management practices play an important role in easing anxiety, which is a widely identified occupational health issue in mergers and acquisitions.

Keywords: acquisition, anxiety, merger, acquirer, target entity, human resource management, uncertainty.

1. Introduction

Business organizations identify mergers and acquisitions (M&A) as a growth strategy with more emphasis on the market and financial aspects of the business. Building on the resource-based view, an organization is comprised of a bundle of resources - tangible and intangible. An organization may not reach its full potential if any of these resources are not under its ownership or control. On the one hand, not having ownership of complementary resources, such as technology, may give an inducement for M&A. On the other hand, not having under control complementary resources, especially human resources, may create difficulties in realizing the expectations of M&A. The literature identifies various driving forces of M&A (refer to Kongpichayanond, 2009; Shook, and Roth, 2011). In the present day, the Covid-19 pandemic can also be identified as a driving force since it influenced a considerable number of businesses to experience either closed down or being acquired by others. The effects of M&A are diverse and impact all stakeholders of the business.

The literature identifies M&A as a human resource game, suggesting that organizations that have human resources to their advantage and under control may succeed in M&A compared to others (Shook and Roth, 2011; Zhang et al., 2015). Many M&As fail to achieve the anticipated outcomes due to various reasons, including issues related to the human side of M&A (Lin et al., 2006; Weber and Tarba, 2010). Human resource-related issues are identified under the three main themes, namely social, cultural, and psychological (Gomes et al., 2012; Marmenout, 2011; Xing and Liu, 2016; Zhang et al., 2015). The social perspective looks at a group of individuals and explains how M&A affects group membership, social comparison, and status. The cultural perspective looks at the organization as a whole and explains how M&A affects sense-making, adjustment, and identity. The psychological perspective looks at the occupational health issues of M&A on individuals and explains their suffering, such as anxiety, and coping.

Our research contributes to the literature on occupational health and M&A by investigating an acquisition that occurred in Sri Lanka. We evaluated employees' experiences of HRM practices, and how these practices affected to ease the level of anxiety due to the M&A across three phases, i.e., pre-M&A, during-M&A, and post-M&A, covering employees from both acquiring and target (acquired) entities. On the one hand, our study investigated employees' evaluation of their experiences covering above mentioned social, cultural, and psychological contexts. On the other hand, although the literature identifies the importance of investigating employees' experience spanning all the phases, empirical research attention gained so far is limited. Further, employees' experiences in the pre-M&A phase were found to influence both during- and post-M&A employees' attitudes and behaviour (Gomes et al., 2012). Furthermore, the phases of during- and post-M&A make substantial changes in the work and social structure of the newly created (merged) organization which could be different to employees' experience with either acquiring and target entities (Marmenout, 2011). Hence, each phase of M&A has its own sources of uncertainty, which give rise to anxiety (Bordia et al., 2004). Empirical studies that cover all the phases of M&A could unearth employees' experiences of HRM practices and their effect in easing anxiety over time. Such understanding is of utmost importance for the well-being of employees, and ultimately M&A success. However, the literature suggests that few research studies investigated human resource issues across each phase of M&A (e.g. Gomes et al., 2012), and we have not found empirical studies that are similar to our study. Therefore, we believe that our study will enhance the understanding in this important area, especially, in a time of Covid-19 pandemic, where the world is witnessing a large number of business entities are acquired by others

(acquirers) due to the operational issues faced by the target entities across industries worldwide (Fairlie, 2020).

Identifying employees' experience of anxiety as a measure of success of M&A, i.e., the lower the level of anxiety the higher will be the M&A success, the present study investigated 1) the level of anxiety experienced by the employees of acquiring and target entities across three phases of merger - pre-, during- and post-M&A, 2) the HRM practices experienced by the employees of acquiring and target entities in each phase of M&A, and 3) the contribution of HRM practices in reducing anxiety experienced by employees across the three phases. Our study has three important features. First, we investigated the experiences of employees from entities. M&A rarely occurs between equals; considerable differences in organization size and power have been observed between the parties of M&A (Panchal and Cartwright, 2001). The literature suggests that the suffering by employees of the target entity is comparatively higher than the employees of the acquiring entity (Panchal and Cartwright, 2001). Second, our sample consisted of employees who survived (or secured their jobs) in the M&A; ours is one of the few studies that investigated the experiences of survivors from both entities. Third, as mentioned earlier, we covered all the three phases of M&A. Third, the study is conducted in a South Asian developing country, Sri Lanka. The country experienced several M&As during the last few decades and these were not identified as successful due to people management issues (Wickramasinghe and Karunaratne, 2009). Since M&As have become more common in the current business environment, especially due to the business environment created by the Covid-19 pandemic, we believe the findings from a developing country will be of interest to academics, practitioners, and policymakers alike worldwide.

2. Review of literature

2.1. Uncertainty and anxiety

Uncertainty is defined as “an individual’s inability to predict something accurately” (Milliken, 1987, p. 136). It is an aversive state with a strong sense of doubt about current or future events (Bordia et al., 2004). Uncertainty can arise due to the lack of sufficient information, ambiguous information, or contradictory information, all of which adversely influence an individual’s ability to predict or control current or future events. According to the literature on uncertainty, one of the negative consequences of an individual’s inability to predict or control current or future events (i.e., uncertainty) is anxiety, where uncertainty and anxiety are positively related (Bordia et al., 2004). Anxiety negatively influences the psychological well-being of individuals, which could lead to changes in work habits, personality and social

behaviour, learned helplessness, and lower performance (Bordia et al., 2004; Colligan and Higgins, 2006). Organizational change has been often identified as a cause for uncertainty (Bordia et al., 2004; Kavanagh and Ashkanasy, 2006). Since M&A is a large-scale organizational change event, uncertainties involved can generate an inordinate amount of anxiety for employees from acquiring and target entities (Ager, 2011; Huy, 2012; Schweiger et al., 1987). The following section reviews the literature to suggest that anxiety could manifest in different ways for employees from acquiring and target entities, and in different phases of M&A.

2.2. M&A, phases of M&A, and employees' experience of anxiety

2.2.1 Merger and acquisition

The literature distinguishes between mergers and acquisitions. A merger is identified as an integration of two or more entities to create a new entity (Schraeder and Self, 2003). It is a mutually accepted incorporation and willing collaboration of two or more entities across different businesses and/or industries. These entities integrate their assets, liabilities, products and services, technology, operations, management practices, and cultural values on a comparatively equal basis (Horwitz et al., 2002). In the post-merger environment, a new work organization is created, in which none of the entities are fully dominant. Hence, a merger neither implies a complete change nor a complete continuation (Van Knippenberg et al., 2002). In contrast, an acquisition is identified as a situation where one entity acquires the ownership of another or a business takeover either in a hostile or friendly environment (Schraeder and Self, 2003). The acquisition gives the acquiring entity to become dominant, and the control of resources and operations of the other (acquired) entity; the acquiring entity can continue to maintain its identity once the new work organization is created (Horwitz et al., 2002; Van Knippenberg et al., 2002). The present study investigated a situation of an acquisition, where in the post-acquisition environment, the acquirer continued to be the dominant entity and the controller of the resources and operations as well as continued to maintain its identity.

2.2.2. The phase after M&A is announced (pre-M&A)

The pre-M&A phase begins with the announcement of the M&A and it continues till the deal is closed (i.e., announcement date to closing date) (Aguilera et al., 2006). Employees often anticipate the worst-case scenario during this period; they may experience anxiety. In particular, employees are likely to be preoccupied with anticipating positive or negative effects as a result of M&A for their future, such as for jobs, livelihoods, and careers (Aguilera

et al., 2006; Seo and Hill, 2005). The announcement of M&A and the associated rumours alone always trigger a variety of negative responses such as hurt, anger, rejection, and disappointment, which may lead to anxiety (refer Aguilera et al., 2006; Buono and Bowditch, 1989; Seo and Hill, 2005 for review). Therefore, Buono and Bowditch (1989) suggest that the level of anxiety may reach its highest level in this phase. However, it is very rare to find specific literature on employees' experiences of anxiety in this phase due to the lack of sufficient research attention received.

2.2.3. M&A integration phase (during M&A)

During this phase, the implementation of M&A occurs. If it is an acquisition, the new owners exert control in myriad ways (Hubbard and Purcell, 2001). Planned change processes are implemented for the integration of core business processes, systems, structure, resources, and management practices for the combined entity. From the people management perspective, the entities involved focus on redesigning work processes, human resource plans, and cultural values for the new entity (Kongpichayanond, 2009). Unlike the pre-M&A phase, interactions between the members of the entities will span beyond top-level management to joint committees to day-to-day operations at each unit level (Kongpichayanond, 2009; Seo and Hill, 2005). The literature also suggests that one of the most important tasks of this phase is to minimize the negative effects that M&A has on the employees of the target entity (Aguilera et al., 2006). The integration phase succeeds only if employees from both entities collaborate and cooperate in the transfer of resources and capabilities. Therefore, the integration phase poses immense challenges for the newly combined entity (Gomes et al., 2012; Seo and Hill, 2005; Weber and Tarba, 2010). Employees may continue to feel anxious over their new job roles, status, reporting authorities, and co-workers in the combined entity (Marks and Mirvis, 1992; Seo and Hill, 2005). If not made clear to the employees in the pre-M&A phase, they may suffer from a lack of information or clear direction (Buono and Bowditch, 1989). Target entity employees, especially, may suffer from feelings of loss of identity and purpose leading to frustration and confusion when they see the target entity ceases to exist (Schweiger et al., 1987). However, the sources of uncertainty and anxiety may be substantially reduced during or by the end of this phase once important decisions on employees' lives are announced, such as new job assignments (Seo and Hill, 2005).

2.2.4. Stabilization phase (post-M&A)

The post-M&A phase begins once the operational integration is accomplished; still, changes and adjustments continue until organizational stability recurs (Kongpichayanond, 2009; Seo

and Hill, 2005). When stabilization continues to achieve, employees may experience that the uncertainties arisen due to M&A gradually decrease (Seo and Hill, 2005). It is also possible to assume that a certain level of trust is built between employees as well as between employees and management (McAllister, 1995). Therefore, post-M&A is an ongoing phase, in which work systems, processes, and performance continue to improve. Still, some stressors may remain at this phase. Specifically, cultural and psychological integration may require more adjustment time beyond what is required for operational integration. Even in the areas of operational integration, the areas that require continuous improvement and fine-tuning may still prevail. Some of such areas within the scope of HRM are job descriptions, the monitoring of employees' performance, compensation plan, and knowledge transfer (Gomes et al., 2012; Kongpichayanond, 2009; Siegenthaler, 2011). Further, if uncertainty and anxiety arose in the pre- and during-M&A phases were not attended sufficiently, these may continue in this phase causing negative outcomes (Andreassi and Grotto, 2011; Bordia et al., 2004). Building on the literature reviewed so far, it is hypothesised:

H1. There are significant differences in employees' experiences of anxiety, where the level of anxiety is higher for employees of the target entity across all phases

H2. There are significant differences in employees' experiences of anxiety, where the level of anxiety is at the highest in the pre-M&A phase and the lowest in the post-M&A phase for both target and acquiring entities.

2.3. HRM practices that reduce uncertainty and anxiety due to M&A

2.3.1. Job role-related practices

Each employee is continuously in the search of information related to the job he/she is going to hold in the newly merged entity since they may not do the same job in the new entity as before. The job-role domain can be divided into job characteristics (what is to be done) and job processes (how it should be done) (Van Maanen and Schein, 1979). Job role-related uncertainties involve ambiguity, overload, autonomy, status differences, geographic transfer, and support networks that could lead to anxiety, fear, and hostility lowering job performance (Andreassi and Grotto, 2011). These can be reduced by implementing job-related HRM practices such as job analysis that leads to creating job descriptions and person specifications (Andreassi and Grotto, 2011; Colligan and Higgins, 2006). Further, the meaningful participation of employees in goal setting, decision-making, and planning and execution of job tasks may give them the capacity to exert influence over his/her environment (Colligan and Higgins, 2006; Lupina-Wegener, 2013). Furthermore, the provision of training on their

job roles gets them accustomed to job changes in the newly merged entity (Schweiger et al., 1987). If appropriate practices are used, job role-related uncertainties could be reduced thereby influencing the level of anxiety experienced by employees. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3: Clarity on job-role reduces employees' level of anxiety

2.3.2. Organization structure and chain of command related practices

From the employees' point of view not only job security is important but also a sense of continuity of the identity of the organization as well as their identity within the newly merged entity are important (Van Dick et al. (2006). The structure that the newly created entity assumes, the chain of command created and the way these are implemented influence the creation of an efficient organizational system (Andreassi and Grotto, 2011). This is also important for employees to develop a self-concept, i.e., "the perception of oneness with or belongingness to an organization, where an individual defines him or herself in terms of the organization(s) in which he or she is a member" (Van Knippenberg et al., 2002). However, maintaining a sense of continuity is difficult since M&A implies discontinuity of the target entity (Van Knippenberg et al., 2002). In acquisitions, knowledge the acquiring entity has on the employees of the target entity in terms of educational qualifications, experience and capabilities are limited; the employees of the target entity may struggle to prove their job performance to the acquiring entity. The fear of demotion when reallocating job positions, the loss of power and status, and unclear career paths may also create uncertainty. Therefore, practices stabilizing the identity of employees in the new organization are important (Andreassi and Grotto, 2011; Van Knippenberg et al., 2002). Employees should be given awareness of organizational hierarchy, reporting relationships, reasons for the existence of different work units, and the location of jobs to reduce much of the uncertainty. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H4: Clarity on organization structure and chain of command reduces employees' level of anxiety

2.3.3. Employment-related practices

Employees seek information on employment-related practices to be expected in the newly formed entity, such as performance management, rewards, and labour relations. Some of the questions employees expect answers are who evaluates performance, what is the performance management procedure, on what basis performance is evaluated, how performance metrics

and compensation systems of the two entities are harmonized (Aguilera et al., 2006; Colligan and Higgins, 2006; Weber and Tarba, 2010). Further, employees expect opportunities for growth; it is important to guide employees of both entities to prepare for career development. Furthermore, employees expect avenues for them to bring out their grievances, active listening to their concerns, and prompt responses to employment-related concerns. The lack of or poorly designed employment-related practices contribute to increasing their anxiety, especially in acquisitions (Lin et al., 2006; Shook, and Roth, 2011; Weber and Tarba, 2010). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H5: Clarity on employment-related practices reduces employees' level of anxiety

2.3.4. Work environment-related practices

The work environment helps employees, especially the target entity employees, to leave the old organization and to enter into the new organization (Aguilera et al. 2006). Interpersonal relationships and group dynamics are primary human-related concerns in M&A. Employees from both entities undergo changes as a result of contact with each other, which is identified as acculturation. An employee may experience workplace stress due to problematic relationships involving managers, co-workers, and subordinates (Colligan and Higgins, 2006). In this regard, interpersonal trust, defined as “the extent to which a person is confident in, and willing to act on the basis of, the words, actions, and decision of another” (McAllister, 1995, p. 25) influences interpersonal and group behaviour. When M&A is viewed from the lens of social capital investment, trust should be developed between as well as within organizational levels (McAllister, 1995). Employees may learn about each other, such as whether colleagues are fair, reliable, and responsible, over time while performing job tasks (Aguilera et al., 2006; Seo and Hill, 2005). Therefore, organization-led initiatives to create a work environment appreciated by employees of both entities are important and essential. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H6: Appreciable work environment reduces employees' level of anxiety

2.3.5. Practices leading to employees' understanding of the direction of the newly merged entity

Employees in both entities are concerned about the strategic direction of the organization and external factors such as technology, market, and future sustainability of the business. Hence, employees should be provided with information for them to understand the acquired entity, and the mission and future direction of the new entity (Aguilera et al., 2006). In this regard, Seo and Hill (2005) state that organization-led interventions such as articulation of new

vision, goals, and organizational symbols could be useful in developing shared understanding as well as helping in the reduction of stress and psychosomatic disorders (Colligan and Higgins, 2006). Building on these previous studies, it is hypothesised:

H7: Clarity on the direction of the newly merged entity reduces employees' level of anxiety

2.3.6. Communicating information about M&A

The communication of information related to the status of M&A is identified as one of the most common and advocated strategies to reduce uncertainty in M&A (Angwin et al., 2016; Bordia et al., 2001). Insufficient and ineffective communication about M&A is identified to increase employees' uncertainty, and thereby negative consequences (Angwin et al., 2016). Therefore, the literature identifies the need of frequent rich, credible, and trustworthy open communication of information about M&A to employees in a timely, coherent, and continuous fashion. On the one hand, a continuous flow of official communication about M&A enable them to gain a better understanding of the M&A, help them to feel both more prepared and able to cope with the M&A reducing anxiety (Angwin et al., 2016; Bordia et al., 2004; Gomes et al., 2012; Vaara and Tienari, 2011). On the other hand, the participatory and interactive nature of communication provides employees with a sense of control over M&A outcomes, implying lower levels of anxiety (Bordia et al., 2004; Colligan and Higgins, 2006). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H8: Communication of information about M&A reduces employees' level of anxiety

2.3.7. Differences by phases of merger and the entity to which employees belonging

Building on the literature reviewed in the above sections on "phases of merger", and "HRM practices", it is possible to assume that differences could exist in terms of the above reviewed six practices between the target entity and acquiring entity as well as between the phases of M&A. Although previous research like Hubbard and Purcell (2001) stated the importance of managing and meeting the expectations of employees of the target entity, we have not found recent empirical research to substantiate whether employees' experiences differ between the two entities or across the phases of M&A. Therefore, the theoretical implications of such a study, like ours, could contribute to several future research. Building on the above-reviewed literature, it is hypothesised:

H9. There are significant differences in employees' experiences in terms of the above reviewed six practices between the target entity and acquiring entity, where more

positive experiences are reported by the employees of the acquiring entity across all phases

H10. There are significant differences in employees' experiences in terms of the above reviewed six practices across the phases of M&A, where these practices are at the lowest in the pre-merger phase for both entities.

3. Methodology

3.1. Sample

The study was on an acquisition that took place in Sri Lanka. The two entities involved were operating in the telecommunication sector, which were identified as the acquiring entity and the target entity. The acquisition is for the entire stake of the target entity for a horizontal expansion of business activities of the newly formed entity. In this regard, Cartwright and Cooper (1996) state same-industry M&A intends to achieve economies of scale and therefore entails a much greater extent of people integration. The acquiring entity held the dominant position throughout the acquisition and in the newly formed entity. After the acquisition, the target entity's name was seized to exist. By the time of the acquisition, the acquirer had 1600 full-time permanent employee base while the target entity had 800 full-time permanent employee base. The acquisition led to a reduction of the employee base of the target entity by fifty percent over the pre- and integration-phases; no employee lay-off occurred in the acquiring entity. The study was conducted one year after the integration phase.

For the study, two samples were selected covering both entities. These employees can be identified as survivors, who had experienced all phases of M&A and by the time of the study full-time engaged in the newly merged entity. The study was cross-sectional in nature and inquired employees' experiences in each phase of M&A. Building on the literature that suggests target entity employees' suffering from anxiety is high with compared to acquiring entity (Aguilera et al., 2006; Seo and Hill, 2005) and the fact that none of the employees attached to the acquiring entity lost their jobs, we invited a larger percentage of employees to volunteer from the target entity. Based on the stratified random sampling technique (refer to Sekaran and Bougie, 2009), the study sample consisted of 80 employees who volunteered from the acquiring entity and 84 volunteered from the target entity. A table detailing the stratification of samples is given in Appendix 1. The valid response rate from the target entity was 92% while it was 65% from the acquiring entity. The demographic information of the respondents is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 about here

3.2. Measures

The perceived level of anxiety due to M&A was measured with the three-item scale developed for the study based on the insights from previous studies such as Aguilera et al. (2006), Buono and Bowditch (1989), and Seo and Hill (2005). These three items were “I felt nervous and stressed very often due to the merger”, “I often felt that difficulties were piling up so high that I could not overcome them due to the merger”, and “I often found that I could not cope with all the things that I had to do due to the merger”. These item measures were on a five-point Likert type response scale ranging from 1 (disagree strongly) to 5 (agree strongly), where higher scores indicate a higher level of anxiety. The perceived clarity of job role, clarity of organization structure and chain of command, clarity of employment-related practices, appreciable work environment, clarity of the direction of the newly merged entity, and communication of information about M&A were measured using the 25-item scale developed for the study. Appendix 2 lists all the item measures used in the study. All the item measures were on a five-point Likert type response scale ranging from 1 (disagree strongly) to 5 (agree strongly), where higher scores indicate a higher level of prevalence. We developed these item measures since previous studies reviewed so far have not provided constructed and tested measures to be used in the study. The item measures were first subjected to a review by academics and academics and practitioners with appropriate background for content and face validity. Thereafter, the measures were pre-tested with a sample of employees from both entities. Upon data collection, the measures were subjected to appropriate internal consistency reliability, factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability, as detailed in the section on *Methods of data analysis*.

With regard to individual and firm characteristics, sex was coded as 0 (male) and 1 (female). Marital status was coded as 0 (single to include never married, separated, divorced, or widowed) and 1 (married). The highest level of education was coded as 0 (Bachelor’s degree or equivalent NVQ level 6) and 1 (postgraduate). Age, the years of work experience in the firm, and job level experience were collected in the ratio scale (years).

3.3. Method of data collection

The self-administered survey questionnaire was used. It was in the English language, which is a national working language of the country. The anonymous survey questionnaire was on three parts, where part one for pre-M&A, part two for during- M&A, and part three for post-

M&A, in which the same item statements were repeated. A printed copy of the questionnaire was distributed together with the covering letter, which detailed the purpose of the study. Respondents from both entities made a voluntary decision to participate anonymously. We adhered to the sample selection criteria stipulated in the section on *Sample*.

3.4. Methods of data analysis

Data were tested for common method variance using Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines (refer to Hair et al. 2006). Principal component factor analysis with Varimax rotation was performed on the variables using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity, and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias. Convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE. We adhered to the thresholds stipulated by Hair et al. (2009). Factor analysis for anxiety resulted in one factor for each phase for each entity (acquiring and target). That is, altogether we created six (6) data tables of factor analysis for anxiety for both entities. Factor analysis for HRM practices resulted in six (6) factors for each phase for each entity. That is, altogether we created six (6) data tables of factor analysis for HRM practices for both entities. These tables were not produced due to article length restrictions. The independent sample t-test was used to understand differences between the two entities and differences between each phase of M&A. Regression analysis was used to identify how far the level of anxiety was predicted by the HRM practices.

4. Results

4.1. Level of anxiety

Table 2 shows the level of anxiety experienced by employees of the two entities across the three phases. The mean values suggest that anxiety is at the highest in the pre-M&A phase for both entities, anxiety is at the lowest in the post-M&A phase. Anxiety experienced by the target entity employees is higher across all the phases, and differences between the two entities were significant in pre-M&A ($t = -3.709, p < .001$) and during-M&A ($t = -1.952, p < .01$) phases; H1 is partially supported.

Table 2 about here

Table 3 shows differences in the level of anxiety experienced by employees across the three phases for each entity. When interpreting the data shown in Table 3 together with mean values shown in Table 2, it is evident that anxiety experienced by target entity employees in the pre-M&A phase is at the highest with compared to during-M&A ($t = -13.083$, $p < .001$) and post-M&A ($t = -24.387$, $p < .001$) phase; anxiety experienced by target entity employees in the during-M&A phase is higher than post-M&A ($t = -9.078$, $p < .001$) phase. This pattern can also be seen for the acquiring entity (refer to the second half of Table 3 together with mean values shown in Table 2). Therefore, as predicted, H2 is supported for both entities.

Table 3 about here

4.2. Practices experienced

As shown in Table 4, differences are significant for the two entities for all the six practices in the pre-M&A phase, for five practices in the during-M&A phase, and for three practices in the post-M&A phase. Therefore, H7 is partially supported.

Table 4 about here

When interpreting the data shown in Table 5 together with mean values shown in Table 4, improvements in practices in the target entity in the post-M&A phase can be observed compared to the pre-M&A. Further, improvements in practices in the target entity can be observed in the post-M&A phase compared to the during-M&A. A similar pattern can be seen for the acquiring entity (refer to the second half of Table 5 together with mean values shown in Table 4). Therefore, H8 is partially supported.

Table 5 about here

To evaluate the relationship between employees' perceptions towards respective organizations' handling of the merger in terms of six practices, correlation and regression were used. A correlation table was created for each entity separately. These two correlation tables were not produced due to article length restrictions. The correlation revealed

relationships are towards the expected directions, satisfying thresholds stipulated by Hair et al. (2009). Individual characteristics were entered into the model in step 1 of the regression analysis. In step 2, six practices were entered into the model. The results of regression analysis for target and acquiring entities are shown in Tables 6 and 7, respectively. As shown in Table 6, job tenure is significant for the employees of the target entity in step 1 as well as in step 2, suggesting it as a significant predictor of anxiety in pre- and during-M&A phases. As can be seen in Table 6 (step 2), the level of anxiety is significantly predicted in the pre-M&A and during-M&A phases by the HRM practices related to the job role, structure and chain of command, direction of the new entity, and communicating information about M&A. In the post-M&A phase too job role, structure, and chain of command and communicating information about M&A plays a significant role. Overall, the adjusted R^2 of .362 in the pre-M&A phase reveals that HRM practices explained 32% of the variance in anxiety ($p < 0.001$); the adjusted R^2 of .294 in the during-M&A phase reveals that HRM practices explained 29% of the variance in anxiety ($p < 0.001$); the adjusted R^2 of .158 in the post-M&A phase reveals that HRM practices explained 16% of the variance in anxiety ($p < 0.001$). Overall, H3, H4, and H6 are supported, and H7 is partially supported for the target entity.

Table 6 about here

As shown in Table 7, job tenure is significant for the employees of the acquiring entity in step 1 as well as in step 2, suggesting it as a significant predictor of anxiety in the pre-M&A phase. As can be seen in Table 6 (step 2), the level of anxiety is significantly predicted in the pre-M&A by the HRM practices related to job role and structure, and chain of command. The HRM practices are not significant in the during- and post-M&A phases, suggesting that the employees of the acquiring entity had not experienced HRM practices as sources of anxiety, When Table 2 is taken into consideration, the anxiety experienced by the employees of the acquiring entity in these two phases are at minimum levels. Overall, H3 and H4 are partially supported.

Table 7 about here

As can be seen from both Table 6 and 7, it is evident that job tenure is the most significant predictor of anxiety of employees attached to both entities. Although not significant, it is evident that age, job tenure, and firm tenure are positively related to anxiety. However, the highest level of education is negatively related to anxiety, implying that employees with lower levels of education qualifications suffer more than employees with higher levels of educational qualifications. Further, married employees suffer more than single employees in our study.

5. Discussion of results in terms of implications for theory and practice

Academic and practitioner-oriented literature identifies the importance of managing anxiety experienced by employees in M&A (such as Lupina-Wegener, 2013). However, we have not found previous empirical studies that investigated the role of HRM practices in easing employees' anxiety due to M&A with the scope of our study for direct comparisons. Our study addressed this gap in the literature. Given the detrimental outcomes that anxiety due to M&A can have on employees and organizations, we believe that our study makes contributions to both existing literature and practice.

5.1. Contribution of the findings to the literature

First, our study is one of the few studies that investigated an acquisition across all the three phases of M&A. Specifically, the unique feature of our study was that it investigated HRM practices as sources of uncertainty that lead to anxiety across pre-, during- and post-M&A phases. Second, we investigated employees' experiences of HRM practices covering employees of both entities. When the level of anxiety experienced across the three phases is compared, the anxiety is at the highest in the pre-M&A phase and lowest in the post-merger phase. Further, the level of anxiety experienced by the employees of the target entity is higher than that of the employees of the acquiring entity across the phases. In our study, acquiring entity is the largest and dominant entity. Hence, it is possible to assume that the target entity was construed as the subordinate; it is also possible to assume that the employees of the target entity feeling less in control, face more workplace changes, and suffer more uncertainty than that of acquiring entity. It is also evident that the employees of the acquiring entity encountered minimal change, and as a result, they experienced low levels of anxiety across all phases of M&A.

We investigated employees' experiences of clarity of job-role, clarity of organization structure and chain of command, clarity of employment-related practices, appreciable work environment, clarity of the direction of the newly merged entity, and communication of

information on M&A. We provided an explanation of psychological effect (anxiety) due to these six areas of the acquisition on the employees of both entities, separately. Our findings suggest that job role, organizational membership, status, and the chain of command are important aspects that create uncertainty and clarity on these reduce the level of anxiety. This suggests that when expectations in terms of these practices seem to be met in the pre- and during-M&A phases, employees seem to be able to form and re-form what they obligate the new entity to provide in terms of people management practices. This is clearly evident from the results of the regression analysis for the target entity. On the one hand, the level of anxiety explained by the six practices is at the highest in the pre-M&A phase, which decreases in the during-M&A phases and further decreases in the post-M&A phase. On the other hand, when the contribution of each practice in explaining anxiety is considered for the target entity, the contribution of job-role is at the highest in the pre-M&A phase, this effect decreases to the lowest level in the post-M&A phase. In this regard, previous research such as Hubbard and Purcell (2001) also suggests that different employee expectations appear during the different phases of the M&A, and these expectations influence their perceived level of anxiety; our study provides empirical support. Our findings also provide empirical support for Bordia et al. (2004), who stated that job-related uncertainties are the most stressful since these have the most personal relevance to an employee. When the statement of Seo and Hill (2005) is taken into account, i.e., “not only the degree but also the duration of uncertainty and anxiety can be a major source of employee stress during M&A”, our findings provide empirical support for a gradual decrease in the sources of anxiety when M&A reaches the post-M&A phase. Although previous research such as Gomes et al. (2012) and Shook and Roth (2011) studied people management practices, these have not covered all the M&A phases. As a result, making direct comparisons to previous research is difficult and implies the importance of the contribution of our study. Therefore, essentially, the findings of our study signify the importance of the human side of M&A and the essential role of HRM practices in reducing anxiety across the phases of M&A.

Another important contribution of the study to the literature is that we investigated survivors of an acquisition from the point of view of both target and acquiring entities. It is possible to assume that when survivors see themselves as being accepted to be part of the newly formed entity they may develop more favourable attitudes that support more changes (in quantity as well as depth) at the workplace. However, more empirical research studies are needed for making conclusions on these lines.

In addition, the findings provided evidence for the importance of employees' age on anxiety, i.e., the older an employee, the more anxious he/she would be. Especially, employees

at the mid-age from the target entity felt more anxious about the acquisition. The effect of age on anxiety was found to be significant across all phases of M&A for the target entity. In a similar vein, the findings showed that married employees are more anxious about the M&A, and low-educated employees are more anxious about the M&A; however, these findings were not significant, and we have not found previous studies to compare with. Therefore, the implications of our study can contribute to much future research in anxiety in the context of M&A.

5.2. Implications for practice

First, the findings provide empirical evidence to suggest the importance of practices related to the job role, structure and chain of command, and communication of information about M&A for the target entity. If organizations plan to minimize surviving employees' turnover in the post-M&A era, they should pay more attention to these practices. These six practices could be used in the management of emotions in M&A. When employees' short-term experiences on these are favourable, they may feel low levels of anxiety. Specifically, the findings showed that the suffering of the target entity employees is significantly higher than that of acquiring entity employees. Second, when differences in practices were considered, it is important for the acquiring entity to shape and then meet the expectations of the employees of the target entity, and all employees in the newly created entity after the merger. Employees of both entities may form expectations on how they will be managed in the newly created entity after the merger.

Third, when the role of communication of M&A information is considered, the findings suggest that these communications could be used to provide the direction of the new entity and the future of individual employees in the new entity. The communications delivered as a stream throughout all the phases of M&A could be used to sell the importance of effective integration of the two entities in the shortest possible time among the surviving employees of both entities.

Forth, findings showed the importance of maintaining an open-door policy and interaction with employees through events like celebrations in the reduction of anxiety due to M&A. On the one hand, this implies the importance of interactions. On the other hand, this implies the importance of equipping managers with skills vital for listening, assisting, and reassuring employees, and helping them to build their informal networks in the newly created entity as well as illustrating behaviours governed by the values of the acquiring entity. As a result, employees, especially target entity employees, may find a psychological assurance to

express opinions, observations, and concerns and questions wherever appropriate while providing strength to implement strategies of the newly created entity.

Fifth, human resource professionals should involve in the management of the emotions of employees as early stages as possible. The findings imply that employees' experiences in the short term could have long-term implications in the newly created entity. As the owners of HRM practices, they have a major role to play in designing, implementing as well as changing/modifying practices appropriately over the period of M&A, and communicating these to employees for assisting them in their transition to the newly created entity.

Sixth, concerning policy-related recommendations, human resource issues in M&As are identified as social, cultural, and psychological (Gomes et al., 2012; Marmenout, 2011; Xing and Liu, 2016; Zhang et al., 2015). The social perspective explains how M&A affects group membership, social comparison, and status. The cultural perspective explains how M&A affects sense-making, adjustment, and identity. The psychological perspective explains human suffering, such as anxiety, and coping. We investigated HRM practices that can improve the conditions related to social and cultural aspects in reducing anxiety. Further, we covered all the phases of M&A to unearth employees' experiences of HRM practices and their effect in easing anxiety over each phase. The study found that employees experience the highest level of anxiety in the pre-M&A phase; the pre-M&A phase experiences were found to influence both during- and post-M&A attitudes and behaviour of employees (Gomes et al., 2012). It was also found that the suffering by the target entity employees is higher than the employees of the acquiring entity across all the phases. Therefore, organizations aiming for M&A should take steps to minimize employees' anxiety in the pre-M&A phase and pay special attention to employee concerns of the target entity. When considering specific HRM practices that are important in M&As, it is evident that job role, structure and chain of command, the direction of the new entity, and communicating information about M&A are important practices for which more attention need to be paid across all the phases of M&A. In detail, job role-related uncertainties in M&A involve ambiguity, overload, autonomy and status differences that could lead to anxiety lowering job performance. These can be reduced by implementing job-related HRM practices such as job analysis. Further, employee participation in goal setting, decision-making, and planning of job tasks may also give them opportunities to exert influence over their work environment. Organization structure and chain of command-related practices help to stabilize the identity of employees in the new organization. Providing awareness of organizational hierarchy, reporting relationships, and different work units and the location of jobs may help to reduce such uncertainties. With regard to practices leading to employees' understanding of the direction of the newly merged

entity, employees have concerns about the strategic direction of the organization and external factors such as market and future sustainability of the new entity. The provision of information about the acquired entity, and the mission and future direction of the new entity could reduce anxiety. With regard to communication-related practices, employees should be frequently communicated credible and trustworthy information about M&A in a timely, coherent, and continuous fashion. In this regard, a continuous flow of information about M&A enables employees to gain a better understanding of the M&A, help them to better prepare and able to cope with the M&A. It is also evident that job tenure is an important predictor of anxiety, where employees with a longer job tenure experiencing higher levels of anxiety. Hence, organizations should pay more attention to employees' job tenure when making employment-related decisions in M&As. Overall, organizations aiming for M&As should understand that the suffering of target entity employees is the highest and the suffering of employees with a longer job tenure is the highest. Further, job role, structure and chain of command, the direction of the new entity, and communicating information about M&A are important practices that organizations should consider most in M&As.

6. Conclusion

This paper presented findings of a study that investigated employees' experiences of anxiety due to M&A and the role of HRM practices in reducing anxiety covering all the phases of M&A. As presented in the section on introduction, our study had several important features that make our study novel. The findings led to identifying the level of anxiety experienced by employees, and differences in terms of the entity to which they belonging to as well as differences in the level of anxiety between each phase within an entity. In a similar vein, the findings were presented and discussed on employees' exposure to HRM practices, and differences in terms of the entity to which they belonging to as well as differences in the HRM practices between each phase within an entity. Further, the results of the regression analysis led to identifying the role of HRM practices in reducing anxiety. Overall, the findings of our study support the argument that the suffering due to anxiety is at the highest in the target entity, and exposure to HRM practices was at the highest in the post-M&A phase. The HRM practices leading to clarity of job role play a significant role across all the phases for the target entity employees. Therefore, the findings of the study have implications for both theory and practice for the reduction of anxiety experienced by employees due to M&A, as discussed in the above sections.

7. Limitations of the study and future research

The paper presented a single situation of acquisition. Being a small island nation, it is very difficult to find the existence of several M&A at one particular point of time to investigate. However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, it is possible to assume that experiences of M&A could be higher in any country context and many individuals may have suffered from anxiety due to M&A experiences. Therefore, building on the findings of the present study several future research studies could be designed. Second, our study was confined to survivors that led us to exclude personal experiences of downsizing as well as how lay-off of colleagues influenced the surviving employees since these are beyond the scope of the present study. Third, in-depth studies can be designed by confining to a single HRM practice for better understanding. Fourth, we used qualitative methodology in the current study. Since anxiety is a human health-related psychological factor, studies based on qualitative methodology may provide more in-depth insights. Fifth, we developed a three-item measure to evaluate the level of anxiety. Future research could validate the suitability of our measure in different country contexts. Overall, as an exploratory study based on acquisition, the investigation has several limitations, at the same time by providing academic and practitioner communities needed but widely unavailable data, we believe that we have opened several future research streams.

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Tables

Table 1: Demographic information

Characteristic	Target entity	Acquiring entity
Sex:		
Male	51.4	58.6
Female	48.6	41.4
Marital status:		
Single	37.3	34.5
Married	62.7	65.5
Highest level of education:		
Bachelor's degree	45.9	25.4
Postgraduate	54.1	74.0
Age:		
Mean	33.34	32.68
SD	6.21	5.83
Minimum	20	21
Maximum	43	42
Firm tenure:		
Mean	3.14	3.76
SD	3.97	2.73
Minimum	1	1
Maximum	12	10
Job tenure:		
Mean	2.22	2.83
SD	1.26	1.71
Minimum	1	1
Maximum	8	7

Table 2: Level of anxiety – between entities

	Pre-M&A			During-M&A			Post-M&A		
	Target entity	Acquiring entity	<i>t</i>	Target entity	Acquiring entity	<i>t</i>	Target entity	Acquiring entity	<i>t</i>
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
Anxiety	4.352 (.641)	4.016 (.611)	-3.709***	3.171 (.873)	2.831 (.821)	-1.952**	2.690 (.657)	2.688 (.592)	-.025

Note: ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 3: Level of anxiety – between phases

	Target entity (<i>t</i>)			Acquiring entity (<i>t</i>)		
	Pre-M&A vs During-M&A	Pre-M&A vs Post-M&A	During-M&A vs Post-M&A	Pre-M&A vs During-M&A	Pre-M&A vs Post-M&A	During-M&A vs Post-M&A
Anxiety	-13.083***	-24.378***	-9.078***	-6.919***	-16.364***	-6.457***

Note: *** $p < 0.001$

Table 4. Practices experienced – between entities

	Pre-M&A			During-M&A			Post-M&A		
	Target entity	Acquiring entity	<i>t</i>	Target entity	Acquiring entity	<i>t</i>	Target entity	Acquiring entity	<i>t</i>
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
Job role-related	3.337 (.567)	3.630 (.570)	3.609***	3.466 (.513)	3.896 (.571)	1.987*	3.947 (.420)	4.149 (.443)	3.213**
Structure and chain of command	3.470 (.510)	3.720 (.687)	4.361***	3.574 (.519)	3.804 (.583)	4.069***	3.588 (.53)	3.889 (.666)	4.610***
Employment-related	3.214 (.537)	3.463 (.590)	3.618***	3.373 (.523)	3.475 (.702)	1.005	3.833 (.421)	3.975 (.527)	1.929
Work environment-related	3.434 (.581)	3.840 (.489)	5.205***	3.460 (.492)	3.862 (.560)	5.490***	3.841 (.467)	4.002 (.449)	2.489*
Direction of new entity	3.402 (.422)	3.750 (.508)	4.408***	3.480 (.583)	3.811 (.662)	5.125***	3.682 (.525)	3.861 (.558)	.885
Information about M&A	3.476 (.384)	3.701 (.459)	3.544***	3.567 (.461)	3.722 (.553)	2.235*	3.762 (.355)	3.948 (.407)	1.516

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 5. Practices experienced – between phases

	Target entity (<i>t</i>)			Acquiring entity (<i>t</i>)		
	Pre-M&A vs During-M&A	Pre-M&A vs Post-M&A	During-M&A vs Post-M&A	Pre-M&A vs During-M&A	Pre-M&A vs Post-M&A	During-M&A vs Post-M&A
Job role-related	.836	5.244***	5.984***	4.015***	6.998***	11.835***
Structure and chain of command	1.590	1.924*	.217	1.313	1.577	1.782
Employment-related	3.776***	4.350***	5.573***	.148	7.731***	8.994***
Work environment-related	.376	4.792***	5.416***	.435	4.031***	2.920**
Direction of new entity	.423	2.004**	2.712***	.454	.602	.073
Information about M&A	1.350	4.518***	2.714**	.441	3.626***	2.034**

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 6: Regression – target entity

Step	Variable	Pre-merger					During-merger					Post-merger				
		beta	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics			beta	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics			beta	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics		
				R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change			R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change			R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change
1	Age	.070	.059	.091	4.227	p < 0.01	.058	.054	.071	5.857	p < 0.01	.069	.014	.010	.412	.840
	Marital status	.026					.084					.032				
	Education	-.012					-.104					-.044				
	Tenure firm	.089					.065					.067				
	Tenure job	.377***					.356***					.030				
2	Age	.048	.362	.293	28.618	p < 0.001	.046	.294	.239	19.472	p < 0.001	.033	.158	.160	9.915	p < 0.001
	Marital status	.021					.066					.060				
	Education	-.023					-.102					-.052				
	Tenure firm	.075					.059					.026				
	Tenure job	.462***					.357***					.084				
	Job role-related	.303***					.346***					.176*				
	Structure and chain of command	-.416***					-.472***					-.211*				
	Employment-related	-.006					-.077					-.098				
	Work environment-related	-.059					-.108					-.087				
	Direction of new entity	-.384***					-.267**					-.053				
	Information about M&A	-.401***					-.231**					-.137*				

Note: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

Table 7: Regression – acquiring entity

Step	Variable	Pre-merger					During-merger					Post-merger				
		beta	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics			beta	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics			beta	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics		
				R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change			R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change			R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change
1	Age	.027	.022	.031	1.081	p < 0.05	.022	.003	.009	.235	.606	.018	.009	.013	.493	.692
	Marital status	.032					.082					.213				
	Education	-.023					-.001					-.082				
	Tenure firm	.067					.003					.162				
	Tenure job	.190*					.104					.053				
2	Age	.100	.127	.154	2.612	p < 0.05	.101	.032	.047	.143	.654	.062	.025	.041	.457	.557
	Marital status	.039					-.104					.214				
	Education	-.019					-.025					-.137				
	Tenure firm	.411					.057					.242				
	Tenure job	.163*					.089					.009				
	Job role-related	-.196*					-.187					-.129				
	Structure and chain of command	-.228**					-.038					-.032				
	Employment-related	-.019					-.017					-.011				
	Work environment-related	-.088					-.053					-.048				
	Direction of new entity	-.065					-.041					-.046				
	Information about M&A	-.016					-.091					-.093				

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Appendix

Appendix 1. Study population, sample selection and responses

Department/ Unit	Study population of newly formed entity*			Study sample (invited to respond)		Sample responded (valid responses)	
	Total study population	Target entity	Acquiring entity	Target entity 20% of the study population	Acquiring entity 5% of the study population	Target entity	Acquiring entity
Information Technology	230	30	200	6	10	6	9
Network Operation	280	80	200	16	10	12	7
Human Resource	45	10	35	4	3	4	3
Finance	290	40	250	8	12	8	12
Sales and Marketing	445	45	400	10	20	10	7
Field Operation team	340	25	315	6	15	6	4
Customer Operation	370	170	200	34	10	31	10
Total	2000	400	1600	84	80	77	52

Notes: *after the merger in full-time permanent employment in the newly formed entity with the experience of pre-during-post merger phases. Employment numbers based on company records

Appendix 2. Item measures

Anxiety:

I felt nervous and stressed very often due to the merger

I often felt that difficulties were piling up so high that I could not overcome them due to the merger

I often found that I could not cope with all the things that I had to do due to the merger

HRM practices:

Job role-related

I had a clear understanding of my job role

I had sufficient time to complete my job duties

I was a participant in deciding changes that directly affect my job tasks

I was given training to prepare for my job role

I was given awareness to get familiar with my job role

Structure and chain of command

I had a clear reporting structure

I was given awareness on how my job fit in the newly merged organization

Each work unit collaborated with each other

Synergy was seen between work units

Employment-related

It was clear to me what are my entitlements for rewards

It was clear to me how my job performance will be evaluated

Promotions were based on our credentials

My career is managed by the organization

Senior management said the door was always open for our concerns and they meant it too

Work environment-related

Employees were enjoying their work

I had good relationships with others

Organization arranged enjoyable social events

Direction of the new entity

I had an understanding of the business case for the merger

I had a clear understanding of how my job contributes to organization achieving its business goals

Planning and goal setting are regular

Information about M&A

Organization did a good job by helping employees to prepare for changes

Organization did a good job communicating regularly on my concerns with the merger

I felt that I am a participant in deciding changes that are directly affecting my life at work

Organization provided information on how well it is performing in the merger process

Our requests about the merger were considered by the management